

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for PKN2 (UniProt ID: Q16513) for use in western blot and flow cytometry

Michael Biddle^{1*}, Jemma Cooper¹, Carolyn Jones², Katie Dixon¹, and Harvinder Virk^{1*}

¹College of Life Sciences, University of Leicester, LE1 7RH, United Kingdom

²Institute for Precision Health, University of Leicester, LE1 7RH, United Kingdom

*Corresponding authors: Michael Biddle (msb65@leicester.ac.uk) and Harvinder Virk (hsv6@leicester.ac.uk)

Abstract

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis is a chronic, progressive interstitial lung disease characterised by fibrotic remodelling of the distal alveolar interstitium and irreversible loss of lung function. Rapid decline in forced vital capacity has been significantly associated with rs115982800, a single nucleotide polymorphism in *PKN2*. Identifying high-quality research antibodies is therefore essential to enable robust investigation of *PKN2* biology and its translational potential. Here, we systematically evaluated eleven commercial antibodies for western blot and flow cytometry using a standardized knockout-validation approach in human HCT 116 cells, comparing readouts in *PKN2* knockout lines with isogenic parental controls. These experiments are part of a broader collaborative initiative addressing antibody reproducibility by characterising commercial antibodies for human proteins and making the results openly available. While antibody performance and protocol conditions may vary between laboratories, this study provides a resource to guide selection of the most suitable reagents for investigations of *PKN2* in health and disease.

Keywords

Q16513, idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, IPF, PKN2, Serine/threonine-protein kinase N2, antibody validation, western blot, flow cytometry.

Introduction

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis is a chronic and progressive interstitial lung disease characterised by fibrosis of the distal alveolar interstitium, leading to progressive decline in lung function. Approved therapeutics such as Pirfenidone and Nintedanib reduce the rate of lung function decline; however, they do not halt or reverse established fibrosis (1). As such, tailored therapies targeting disease pathogenesis and progression through precision medicine approaches may improve treatment outcomes and support the identification of patients with increased disease susceptibility. One approach to identify candidate therapeutic targets is the investigation of disease-associated single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), such as variants in *PKN2* (rs115982800), which have been associated with rapid decline in forced vital capacity (2). The encoded protein, Serine/threonine-protein kinase N2 (PKN2), regulates activation of Rho GTPases, thereby mediating actin cytoskeletal organisation (3). However, detailed investigation of PKN2 biology and its potential role in disease requires well-validated research tools, including reliable antibodies for protein detection and characterisation.

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterising commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols (4) and openly sharing the data (5). Here we evaluated the performance of eleven commercial antibodies for PKN2

for use in western blot and flow cytometry, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of PKN2 properties and function. The platform for antibody characterisation used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterisation procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardised consensus antibody characterisation protocols are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterisation data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret the antibody characterisation data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (6).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT (wild type) and KO cells (7-9). The first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcript per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655). The HCT 116 cell line expresses the *PKN2* transcript at $5.1 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a *PKN2* KO HCT 116 cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1).

To screen all eleven PKN2 antibodies by western blot, protein lysates from both HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cell lines were run on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes and probed in parallel with eleven PKN2 antibodies (Figure 1).

For flow cytometry, HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. Both cell lines were fixed, permeabilised and blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. Eleven PKN2 antibodies were then evaluated, with fluorescent intensity assessed using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Antibody staining in both WT and KO line was then quantified using FlowJo software, with representative histograms presented in Figure 2.

In conclusion, we screened eleven PKN2 commercial antibodies by western blot and flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced using human HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells. High-quality and renewable antibodies capable of successfully detecting PKN2 were identified.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available PKN2 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance

without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in PKN2, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. PKN2 experts are invited to analyse and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots. Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Methods

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io (DOI: [dx.doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)).

Antibodies

All PKN2 antibodies are listed in Table 2, together with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRID), to ensure antibodies are cited properly (10). Secondary antibodies used in this study are provided in Table 3. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations.

Cell culture

All cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1, alongside their corresponding RRIDs, to ensure proper citation (11). Cells were cultured in DMEM (Capricorn Scientific #DMEM-HPSTA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific #A5256801) and 1% antibiotic/antimycotic solution (Capricorn Scientific #AAS-B). All cell lines used in this study were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

Antibody screening by western blot

For lysate preparation, HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells were washed three times in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #70011044) and lysed in RIPA buffer containing 1x of protease inhibitor cocktail, sodium orthovanadate and phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (Santa Cruz Biotechnology #sc-24948). Lysates were sonicated (40% amplitude for 5 seconds) three times and incubated for 30 minutes on ice prior to centrifugation at 20,000 x g for 1 hour at 4°C.

Protein concentration was confirmed using the Pierce BCA protein assay (Thermo Fisher Scientific #23225) and 30µg of protein was used. Samples were combined with Laemmli sample buffer (Bio-Rad #1610747) containing 2-mercaptoethanol (final concentration 355mM) (Sigma Aldrich #M7522) before being heated at 65°C for 10 minutes. Samples were then loaded in precast 4-20% WedgeWell Tris-Glycine Plus midi gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific #WTG42020BOX) alongside Prime-Step prestained broad range protein ladder (BioLegend #773302). SDS-PAGE was then performed in SureLock Tandem Midi Gel tanks (Thermo Fisher Scientific #STM1001) and run at 200V for 1 hour with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad #1610772). Proteins were then transferred to 0.2µm supported nitrocellulose membranes (Cytiva #10600015) using a Criterion blotter with plate electrodes (Bio-Rad #17004070) run at 85V for 45 minutes. Proteins on the blot were visualised with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific #161470250) which was scanned to show alongside individual western blots. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hour except for antibody 8697 which was blocked in 5% BSA in Tris-buffered saline containing 1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J77500.K2). Primary antibodies were then incubated overnight at 4°C in 5% milk TBST with gentle shaking. Following three ten-minute washes with TBST, horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugated secondary antibodies were incubated at a dilution of 1/10000 (0.1µg/mL) in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hour at room temperature followed by three ten-minute washes with TBST. Membranes were then incubated with either Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific #32106) for 1 minute or Clarity Western ECL substrate (Bio-Rad #1705061) for 5 minutes prior to detection with the ImageQuant LAS 4000.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells were detached, and five million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet, fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, #C7025 and #C10094). WT and KO cells were centrifuged at 300 x *g*, for 10 minutes and resuspended in PBS containing 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma-Aldrich, A9647). The two populations were combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 minutes using 800 µL of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific #J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA in PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilised in 400 µL PBS with 0.1% Saponin (Sigma-Aldrich #558255) for 10 minutes at room temperature, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum (Sigma-Aldrich #G6767), 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin in PBS for 30 minutes on ice. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C and incubated in 150µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% Saponin PBS with primary *PKN2* antibodies for 30 minutes on ice. 500µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C. Cells were then incubated with their corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies (Table 3) in 150 µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS for 30 minutes on ice. 500 µL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged 600 x *g* for 15 minutes at 4°C.

Tubes were then resuspended in 1 ml of 1% BSA in PBS and data was acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer. Data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. The cell population was first gated on FSC-A vs SSC-A, within that gate single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations compared to the two secondary only controls. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: [Dataset for the PKN2 antibody screening study <DOI>](#)

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1. Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalogue number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	AB255451	CVCL_0291	HCT 116	WT
Abcam	AB266894	CVCL_B1DY	HCT 116	PKN2 KO

Table 2. Summary of the PKN2 antibodies tested.

Company	Catalogue number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Stock concentration (µg/mL)	Vendor recommended applications
Abcam	ab138514**	1037490-5	AB_3668835	Monoclonal Recombinant	EPR5490	Rabbit	-	ICC/IF, WB
Abcam	ab314021**	1075349-3	AB_3668836	Monoclonal Recombinant	20A8	Rabbit	400	Intra-FC, ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Abclonal	A19746**	4000002274	AB_3668860	Monoclonal Recombinant	ARC2274	Rabbit	400	ELIAS, ICC/IF, WB
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP61894_P050	QC32618-40750	-	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	500	WB
Cell Signalling Technology	8697**	1	AB_2797651	Monoclonal Recombinant	D10A10	Rabbit	100	IP, WB
Proteintech	14608-1-AP	00011209	AB_10638487	Polyclonal	-	Rabbit	450	ELISA, FC, ICC/IF, IHC, IP, WB
R & D Systems	MAB5686*	CBZH0124031	AB_2163979	Monoclonal	509105	Mouse	500	WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-15887*	ZJ4521294	AB_11155620	Monoclonal	1D1	Mouse	-	ELISA, FC, ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-37978**	ZJ4521739	AB_2897896	Monoclonal Recombinant	ARC2274	Rabbit	400	IP, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-44818**	ZJ4520956C	AB_2931275	Monoclonal Recombinant	JE62-44	Rabbit	1000	ICC/IF, IHC, WB
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-49998**	ZJ4520724A	AB_3092493	Monoclonal Recombinant	20A8	Rabbit	400	ELISA, FC, ICC/IF, IHC, WB

* Monoclonal antibody, ** Recombinant antibody.

ELISA = Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, FC = Flow cytometry, ICC/IF = Immunocytochemistry/ immunofluorescence, IHC = immunohistochemistry, IP = immunoprecipitation, WB = Western blot.

Table 3. Summary of the secondary antibodies used.

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalogue number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Application	Stock concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Working concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	Recombinant Polyclonal	Western blot	1000	0.1
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Rabbit (H + L)	RGAR005	AB_3073509	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625
Proteintech	Coralite-Plus-647-Goat Anti-Mouse (H + L)	RGAM005	AB_3073503	Recombinant Polyclonal	Flow cytometry	500	0.625

Figure 1: Serine/threonine-protein kinase N2 antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Serine/threonine-protein kinase N2 antibody screening by flow cytometry

Figure legends

Figure 1: PKN2 antibody screening by western blot using protein lysates

Protein lysates from HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells were collected, and 30µg of protein was used for western blot with the indicated PKN2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO samples. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab138514** at 1/1000, ab314021** at 1/1000, A19746** at 1/1000, ARP61894_P050 at 1/500, 8697** at 1/1000, 14608-1-AP at 1/1000, MAB5686* at 1/500, MA5-15887* at 1/1000, MA5-37978** at 1/1000, MA5-44818** at 1/1000, and MA5-49998** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 112.0kDa. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: PKN2 antibody screening by flow cytometry

HCT 116 WT and *PKN2* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% saponin. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated PKN2 antibodies and corresponding Multi-rAb CoraLite® Plus 647 secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer with representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line). Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. Antibody dilutions used: ab138514** at 1/1000, ab314021** at 1/4000, A19746** at 1/4000, ARP61894_P050 at 1/500, 8697** at 1/1000, 14608-1-AP at 1/4500, MAB5686* at 1/500, MA5-15887* at 1/1000, MA5-37978** at 1/4000, MA5-44818** at 1/10000, and MA5-49998** at 1/4000. ** = recombinant antibody, * = monoclonal antibody.